

ExPaNDS Data Landscaping Survey

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1. Introduction

The ExPaNDS project is a collaboration between 10 national Photon and Neutron Research Infrastructures (PaN RIs) as well as EGI. The project aims to deliver standardised, interoperable, and integrated data sources and data analysis services for Photon and Neutron facilities, within the context of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). As part of its programme, it is considering how to enable and promote the generation and use of FAIR data within facilities' processes (work package 2), and the harmonisation of tools and processes for data cataloguing and management (work package 3).

WP2 and WP3 are conducting a landscape analysis in order to establish a baseline on the current state of the 10 participating institutions on FAIR data policies and data management practises. This activity can be compared with a similar activity which was undertaken within the PaNOSC project, which covers the transnational (ESFRI) facilities in the same domain. This baseline can then be used to steer the subsequent activity of the project and to assess its impact.

This report summarises the results of a survey of the 10 participating institutes which was undertaken in December 2019.

2. Data Policy

The National Research Facilities represented in ExPaNDS have been actively developing data policy. All the facilities report that they either have a Data Policy in place, or else they are in the process of agreeing a policy in their institution. Some have had policies in place for some years which have gone through several revisions.

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	Does your organization have a Data Policy (DP) defined?	When was the last version of the DP released?	
HZDR	Yes	26/06/2018	
Max-IV	Yes	19/01/2017	
CELLS-ALBA	Yes	1/07/2017	https://www.cells.es/en/users/call-information-1/bases/2017_07_data_policy_alba_approved-cr.pdf
PSI	Yes	30/11/2016	https://www.psi.ch/en/science/psi-data-policy
DLS	Yes	18/12/2018	https://www.diamond.ac.uk/Users/Policy-Documents/Policies/Experimental-Data-Management-Pol.html
DESY	In progress		
SOLEIL	Yes	2/10/2018	https://www.synchrotron-soleil.fr/en/file/11308/download?token=96KVRymM
HZB	Yes	19/01/2017	https://hz-b.de/datapolicy
ELETTRA	Yes	1/12/2014	https://vuo.elettra.eu/vuo/cgi-bin/download-tm4.py?frm_user_id=8707&frm_iddocumenttype=14&frm_iddocument=208454&frm_hash=efb046860392bdb106d0e8c91e9cea57e465cf7e
UKRI-ISIS	Yes	currently under revision.	https://www.isis.stfc.ac.uk/Pages/Data-Policy.aspx

2.1. General Principles

The Data Policies generally include advice and guidelines on principles and practises behind the policy. All 9 facilities which have a published policy include general principles, with between 2 and 17 clauses and definitions identified.

The development of data policies in this community is influenced by the PaNDATA Data Policy Framework¹, which predates the development of the FAIR data principles. Consequently, the explicit treatment of FAIR data principles in the Data Policy is mixed:

Question	Response
Does the DP mention the FAIR principles explicitly ?	3 Yes 7 No

Where FAIR is mentioned, the motivations for collecting FAIR is included in the Policy. Several institutes report that while they do not explicitly mention FAIR, they do cover the motivations and benefits of openness:

¹https://www.panosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/PaN-data-D2.1_PolicyFramework.pdf

<p>What are these motivations (for FAIR Data)?</p>	<p>Open Access, Funders Requirements, Visibility</p> <p>Open Data is included</p> <p>Since FAIR is not mentioned explicitly the motivations for FAIR are not explicitly included either; although they may be described inter alia in other sections</p> <p>Contribute to scientific dialogue and advances, by allowing researchers to benefit from and improve previous work thanks to the reuse of data collected from experiments performed on SOLEIL instruments, once made openly accessible</p> <p>Although FAIR data is not explicitly mentioned, the DP refers to good scientific practice and the requirement for Open Data.</p> <p>FAIR data should make our facility more productive in general terms. FAIR data are also inline with the official "mission and vision" of the ELETTRA.</p>
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And further good data management practices are generally explicitly covered in Policies.

Question	Response
<p>Are Good Practices listed in the DP?</p>	<p>9 Yes 1 No</p>
<p>What Good Practices are listed?</p>	<p>Safeguarding Good Scientific Practice and Proceeding in Case of Scientific Malpractice</p> <p>Keeping metadata as complete as possible, best efforts made to capture relevant metadata</p> <p>Experimental team to ensure metadata are as complete as possible; Provide means for the capture of metadata; Acknowledgement of the source of the data and citation of its unique identifier as well as any publications linked to the same raw data; Encouraging the link of the results of the analyzed data with the raw data / metadata using online catalogues.</p> <p>1. The experimental team is encouraged to ensure that experiments metadata are as complete as possible, as this will enhance the possibilities for everybody to search for, retrieve and interpret the data in the long term.</p>

	<p>2. One site plans to provide means for the capture of such metadata items that are not automatically captured by an instrument, in order to facilitate recording the fullest possible description of the raw data.</p> <p>3. Researchers who aim to carry out analyses of raw data and metadata which are openly accessible should, where possible, contact the original PI to inform her/him and suggest a collaboration if required. Researchers must acknowledge the source of the data and cite its unique identifier as well as any publications linked to the same raw data.</p> <p>4. PIs and researchers who carry out analyses of raw data and metadata are encouraged to link the results of these analyses to the raw data / metadata using the facilities provided by the on-line catalogue. Furthermore, they are encouraged to make such results openly accessible</p> <p>Main proposer and/or experimental team : ensure that metadata are as complete as possible, including sample descriptions and experiment number correctly entered into the metadata for each raw data set ; ensure that any information, including personal data, added by the experimental team into the metadata, comply with the French and European data protection regulations; ensure that the experimental team agrees on any change of the embargo period; respond to requests about data obtained from the experiment once openly accessible</p> <p>Researchers: before carrying out analyses of openly accessible data, contact the original Main Proposer, to inform, suggest collaboration and propose to be co-author in any future publication arising from the data, if appropriate ; when publishing results, acknowledge the source of the data, cite its unique persistent identifier and any publications linked to the same raw data or the origin of the raw data.</p> <p>Capture of metadata, researchers using raw data are encouraged to cooperate with the original experimental team & to link the raw data</p> <p>"The experimental team is encouraged to ensure that experiments metadata are as complete as possible, as this will enhance the possibilities for them to search for, retrieve and interpret their own data in the future."</p>
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	<p>5.1 The experimental team is encouraged to ensure that experimental metadata are as complete as possible, as this will enhance the possibilities for them to search for, retrieve and interpret their own data in the future.</p> <p>5.2 ISIS undertakes to provide facilities for the capture of such metadata items that are not automatically captured by an instrument, in order to facilitate recording the fullest possible description of the raw data.</p> <p>5.3 Researchers who aim to carry out analyses of raw data and metadata which are publicly accessible should, where possible, contact the original PI to inform them and suggest a collaboration if appropriate.</p> <p>5.4 PIs and researchers who carry out analyses of raw data and metadata are encouraged to link the results of these analyses with the raw data / metadata using the facilities provided by the on-line catalogue.</p> <p>Furthermore, they are encouraged to make such results publicly accessible.</p>
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Some data policies include information on the processes involved in the enactment of the policy; however, some would see that this would be out of scope of the policy.

Question	Response
Does your DP include well defined processes?	2 Yes 5 No 3 Not applicable
Please list the processes names and a brief explanation.	Raw Data Handling, Meta Data Capture, Data Publication, Data Archiving Data production, reduction and analysis process; data storage and curation; data access and reuse

2.2. Policy Content

The data policies always cover the raw data generated by the facilities instruments. Most policies go further to consider the data resulting from subsequent processing and analysis. This typically would clarify ownership and encourage users to manage the processed data in an open manner.

Question	Response
Does the DP cover the Raw Data?	10 yes 0 no

Does the DP cover the Processed Data?	7 yes 3 no
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Policies can also cover how other information may be stored and released. In particular, the experimental proposal is an area which is often considered. This gives information on the experimental context which is important for subsequent reuse; however, user may consider that it contains sensitive Intellectual property. Thus facilities give it special consideration,

Question	Responses
What access to proposals is foreseen in DP?	<p>3 reported no general access. Others said.</p> <p>Open Access recommended</p> <p>Provided by the principal investigator or experimental team on request.</p> <p>Public for Regular user calls, friendly users and training experiments, in-house research, access derived from formal collaboration agreement and the use of management contingency beam-time.</p> <p>Available after the experiment has been carried out (high level metadata only)</p> <p>An on-line catalog, accessible to registered users, will enable linking experimental data to experimental proposals. Access to proposals will only be provided to the experimental team and appropriate facility staff, unless otherwise requested by the Main Proposer.</p> <p>Proposal metadata is treated as any other metadata. It becomes openly accessible together with related raw data after expire of embargo period.</p> <p>Some elements are in the public domain, e.g. PI, Col, institutions and abstracts otherwise access restricted to experimental team and authorised Staff.</p>

The relationship of the institutional Data Policy to the user's Data Management Plan is emerging as an important factor in the application of policy. Some Data Policies are now giving explicit consideration to DMPs.

Question	Response
Does the DP include information related to users Data Management plan?	3 Yes 7 No

<p>What are the requirements of the Data Management plan ?</p>	<p>Appendix: Checklist for a Data Management Plan</p> <p>Posing a recommendation to have a DMP</p> <p>The Main Proposer (MP) is required to establish a Data Management Plan. SOLEIL can bring help by providing a template (to be defined) or by sending out the available information to the MP if the funder or research institution or other organization has particular data management requirements.</p>
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Data Licence is considered in most of the policies, with others reporting this is an aspect which is being developed, with the adoption of CC licences.

Question	Response
<p>Under what License data are made available?</p>	<p>1 CC0 4 CC-BY 1 CC-BY-SA 4.0 1 CC0 and CC-BY as alternatives</p> <p>3 no licence currently specified, though one RI plans to introduce a CC licence in its next revision.</p>

Data protection and the GDPR regulations is another area which has become more prominent since the development of the PaNDATA data policy framework, and Data Policies are now beginning to cite it explicitly. Note that Data Protection would also typically be covered within the policies and general terms and conditions of the use of the facility.

Question	Response
<p>Does the DP mention/treats the GDPR?</p>	<p>1 Treats 3 Mentions 6 None of these</p>

Further criteria covered in the policy are discussed in the following sections.

3. Metadata standards

Although all ExPaNDS RI facilities replied that their Data Policy covers metadata explicitly, only two of them have specific metadata standards defined, and another one mentions HDF5 as the standard specified in this particular section of the questionnaire.

Some of the responses justified this lack of explicit standards as a way to provide flexibility to the

metadata definition along the time.

Question	Response
Does the DP cover Metadata?	12 Yes 0 No
What are the standards of Metadata used (or mentioned) in the DP (if any)?	2 Daticite 9 None/Blank/"Barely mentioned" 1 HDF5

3.1. Metadata collection

There is quite a variety of different services provided to users to capture metadata. All RIs claim to provide human-interaction tools for enriching the data capture with metadata, such as Notebooks or Elogbook. Confluence, Google Docs, and Slack have also been mentioned on the various responses received.

On the other hand, RIs have also mentioned different automatic metadata ingestion systems such as GDA (data acquisition software), OpenBIS (institutional data management software), or simple scripting.

There is no detected standard tooling for any of these two types of processes among the different RIs, although the need is quite common.

Question	Response
How do your users collect Metadata during the experiment?	6 Notebook 7 Elogbook 1 Scripts 5 Automatic capture during acquisition OpenBIS, Special macros,
Other tools your institution is offering to users (Data catalogues, logbooks, etc...)	RODARE (Publication Platform), Metadata Catalogue (ICAT, SciCAT), OpenBIS, ISPyB as LIMS, VUO (includes a catalogue, Jupyter Notebook and HDF5 browser)

4. Identifiers

Facilities policies and practises are increasingly using Persistent identifiers

Question	Response
Does the DP mention the Persistent Identifier need? (e.g. DOI)	5 Yes 5 No
What are Persistent identifier defined for in the DP?	3 Data DOI for experiment and dataset 1 for publications only 1 mentions in DP, but has not issued as yet 1 is not mentioned in the DP, but does issue DOIs 3 institutes are not currently issuing DOIs but plan to in the next ear future.

Some facilities are also engaging with the efforts to user public identifiers for users, such as ORCID.

Question	Response
Do you promote the usage of Public Identifier for users (e.g. ORCID)?	4 Yes 6 No
What Public Identifier for users are you promoting?	ORCID

5. FAIR data training

The ExPaNDS RI facilities host several thousand academic and commercial researchers for competitive peer reviewed or commercially contracted experiments annually. Additionally the RIs host inhouse scientists, support staff and software and technique development teams. The survey of ExPaNDS reveals that currently there is little in the way of training. One of the goals of the project is to address this in WP 5 for both inhouse staff and user communities.

Question	Response
Do you offer any kind of training related to FAIR data to your users?	1 Yes 8 No
Please list the trainings you are offering to users?	One facility: Open Access Publication
Are you offering any training (scientific, IT,...) to your staff in order to comply with FAIR data principle?	3 Yes 6 No
Please list the training you are offering to your staff	One facility: Open Access Publication One facility: Research integrity information for PhD students and postdocs One facility: Introduction to the principles and explanation of the DP.

6. Data Catalogues

The Expands RI facilities are providing cutting edge experiments to either public or industrial users. Data constitutes a main asset to advance scientific research especially when combined with data sharing and reuse. In the last few years, two main data catalogues have been developed and are currently in use in some X-ray and Neutron facilities: ICAT (including ICAT+) and SciCat. Other facilities are still investigating or currently developing their own data catalogue. For many facilities, the data catalogue will provide access to data and the ability to make data publicly available after an embargo period.

Question	Response
Data catalogue used	Icat: 3 facilities Icat+: 1 facility SciCat: 2 facilities Custom: 2 facilities Custom but investigating alternatives: 1 facility Under investigation: 2 facilities
Data catalogue url	Url provided: 7 facilities
Login required (non Anonymous access)	Yes: 6 facilities No: 1 facility NA: 3 facilities
File formats archived	only hdf5: 1 facility only Nexus and hdf5: 2 facility Only Nexus, hdf5, ascii, spec: 1 facility Only Nexus, hdf5,ascii, tiff: 1 facility Only Nexus, ASCII, ISIS RAW, image formats: 1 facility All formats generated: 3 facilities NA: 1 facility
Database used for metadata of data catalogue	MongoDB: 2 facilities PostGresql + MongoDB: 1 facility Oracle: 3 facilities MariaDB: 1 facility Oracle +PostgreSQL: 1 facility NA: 2 facilities
Primary software language of data catalogue interface	Javascript: 2 facilities Java: 2 facilities Java + javascript: 2 facilities Python + PL/SQL: 1 facility NA: 3 facilities
Main technology of data catalogue interface	Angular: 5 facilities React: 1 facility NA: 4 facilities

Number of public dataset/files	28027: 1 facility 15520/43845: 1 facility 14872: 1 facility 61: 1 facility 0: 3 facilities NA: 3 facilities
Using OAI-PMH	Yes: 1 facility No: 7 facilities NA: 2 facilities
Minting DOIs	Yes: 2 facilities No: 3 facilities In progress: 3 facilities NA: 2 facilities
Data embargo policy	No embargo: 1 facility (data is the property of the PI) 5 years: 1 facility 3 years: 4 facilities 3 years extensible to 4 years: 1 facility 3 years extensible twice a year with justification: 1 facility Will be Pan-compliant: 1 facility NA: 1 facility
Data embargo policy url	URL provided: 6 facilities
Number of instruments connected to the data catalogue	0: 2 facilities 1: 1 facility 2: 1 facility 10: 1 facility 20: 1 facility 37: 1 facility 39: 1 facility NA: 2 facilities

(NA stands for Not Available)

APPENDIX 1

ExPaNDs LANDSCAPING SURVEY – COMPLETED BY 13TH DECEMBER

ExPaNDs - WP2 & WP3: The mainstreaming of standards for data management & Metadata Catalogue

Data Policy

* required

Does your organization have a Data Policy (DP) defined? *

- Yes
- No
- In progress

When was the last version of the DP released?

MM / DD / 2019

Does the DP include a version number? *

- Yes
- No
- NA

Does the DP have a section on General Principles? *

- Yes

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- No
- NA

How many terms are included in the General Principles ? *

Your answer _____

Does your DP include well defined processes? *

- Yes
- No
- NA

Please list the processes names and a brief explanation.

Your answer _____

Does the DP include information related to users Data Management plan? *

- Yes
- No
- NA

What are the requirements of the Data Management plan?

Your answer _____

Does the DP mention the FAIR principles explicitly ? *

- Yes
- No
- NA

Are the motivations of collecting FAIR data included in the DP? *

- Yes
- No
- NA

What are these motivations?

Your answer _____

Does the DP mention/treats the GDPR? *

- Mentions
- Treats
- Mentions & Treats
- None of the above

Does the DP cover the Raw Data? *

- Yes
- No
- NA

Does the DP cover the Metadata? *

- Yes
- No
- NA

What are the standards of Metadata used (or mentioned) in the DP (if any)?

Your answer_____

Does the DP cover the Processed Data? *

- Yes
- No
- NA

Does the DP mention the Persistent Identifier need? (e.g. DOI) *

- Yes
- No
- NA

What are Persistent identifier defined for in the DP? *

Your answer_____

Do you promote the usage of Public Identifier for users (e.g. ORCID)? *

- Yes
- No

What Public Identifier for users are you promoting?

Your answer _____

What access to proposals is foreseen in DP? *

Your answer _____

Are Good Practices listed in the DP? *

- Yes
- No
- NA

What Good Practices are listed?

Your answer _____

Under what License data are made available? *

Your answer _____

Is anonymous access allowed?

- Yes
- No
- NA

